

Evaluation Guide: OpenUPExp Framework (Trademark Registration Scenario)

To conduct the evaluation, please follow the workflow below:

Step 1: Familiarization and Context (Mandatory)

Before starting, it is essential to understand the business scenario (Trademark Registration) and the logic behind the construction of the agents (Workers).

- **Illustrative Scenario:** *Illustrative Scenario - initial phase - OpenUPExp*
- **Presentation Video (6 min):** Watch the Flow Video – *Overview of the implementation in Langflow*

Supporting Materials (Flow Inputs)

- **Worker 1 (Scope):** Input Document – *Trademark_Registration_Scope.pdf*
- **Worker 5 (RAG Knowledge Base):** RAG Documents

Step 2: Artifact Exploration (Choose One Option)

Option 1: Direct Inspection in Langflow

This option allows navigation through prompt engineering and execution of the flow in real time.

1. Access the environment: Go to astra.datastax.com (Login via Google or GitHub)
2. Open Langflow: Click the Langflow icon in the left-side menu
3. Import the Artifact: Click “New Project” (or the + icon) and select “Upload File”
4. JSON File: Upload the file *OpenUPExp_Explainability_Vision.json*
5. Execution (Optional): To run the flow, insert your Groq key in *Global Variables* (gear icon in the bottom-left corner) using the name: *groq_api_key*

Option 2: Document-Based (Static) Analysis

Recommended for an evaluation focused on concepts and generated outputs.

- **Architecture Guide:** [Access here] – Contains the logic of each Worker, structured prompts, and generated outputs

Step 3: Evaluation Task and Feedback (Mandatory)

Based on your understanding of the scenario and the framework, perform the final validation [Access here].